

Social and Political Effects of Digital Transformation

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Niyaz Bokvadze

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Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER

St. Clements University
Psychology Department
Head Lecturer

Orcid ID: 0000-0001
5896-2956

Mail:

kursatshinyildirimer@gmail.com

Dr. Cüneyt Yılmaz

St. Clements University
Political Sciences MSB

Orcid ID: 0000-0003-1655-588X

cuneytymz53@gmail.com

Abstract

This article explores the development of cultural identities on digital platforms and the influence of these identities on political and social interactions. This analysis centers on the impact of digital revolution on cultural diversity and the creation of online identity politics. Online platforms enable individuals to express and reinforce their cultural identities, but they can also facilitate cultural conflicts. The article examines the political and social consequences of the development of cultural identities on

the internet and explores topics such as safeguarding or stifling diversity. Hence, comprehending the impacts of digital transformation on cultural identities is a substantial challenge and potential for political decision-makers. This article seeks to enhance comprehension of cultural identities and politics on online platforms within political and social contexts.

Keywords: Online identities, Cultural diversity, Digital transformation, Political impacts

INTRODUCTION

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Digital transformation is the term used to describe the significant impact that rapid advancements in communication technology have on the political and social structures of societies. This transition arose because of the advancements introduced by the post-modern era. The proliferation of the Internet and advancements in communication technologies have facilitated the transition of individuals' daily activities to digital platforms. The notion of a "network society" is a fundamental characteristic of this emerging social epoch. The concept of network society describes a societal framework where individuals build their daily routines around internet networks, communication is transformed into digital form, and information technology are extensively utilized in all aspects of life. The emergence of this novel social framework has resulted in significant transformations across various domains, encompassing the development of personal identities and the dynamics of social interactions. Effective communication is an essential tool for comprehending the social and political consequences of digital transition. Political communication not only influences individuals' political beliefs and attitudes, but also establishes social norms and behavioral patterns. Studies indicate that communication significantly influences the overall political culture and societal norms (Zaller, 1992). It is crucial to comprehend the societal and political impacts of digital communication to grasp the intricacies and fluidity of contemporary cultures. The significance of the media should not be disregarded. The media not only influences the overall perspectives and political awareness of society, but it also plays a crucial role in shaping social norms (Entman, 2012). Hence, the impact of media on political communication is crucial in shaping society's political beliefs and affecting engagement in political activities. Gaining insight into the societal and political consequences of digital change is crucial for comprehending the intricacies and ever-changing nature of contemporary society. It is imperative to thoroughly analyze the impact of swift changes and advancements in communication technologies on the political and social frameworks of societies to formulate forward-thinking policies and effectively manage societal transformation. This essay analyzes the development of cultural identities on digital platforms and the impact of these identities on political and social processes. This analysis will specifically explore the impact of digital transformation on cultural diversity and the significance of online identity policies in facilitating this process. This analysis will examine the political and social

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ramifications of the development of cultural identities on online platforms. It will also explore the significance of safeguarding or repressing variety in political and social spheres.

AIM

This essay seeks to explore the intricacies of cultural identity development on online platforms and the subsequent impact of these identities on political and social dynamics. The impact of digital transformation is evident in contemporary society, as advancements in internet and communication technologies are fundamentally altering the social fabric. These developments are occurring in a setting where cultural diversity is further escalating. The term "network society" describes a time when social interactions are conducted using digital technologies and online identities have greater significance. Currently, people's online identities play a crucial role in shaping their self-expression and social interactions in their day-to-day existence. Hence, the study of cultural identities' development on online platforms and their impact on political and social outcomes is a significant field of research. The objective of this paper is to comprehensively examine the development of cultural identities on online platforms and assess the impact of these identities on political and social dynamics. This analysis seeks to comprehend the influence of digital revolution on cultural variety and underscore the political and social significance of safeguarding or stifling difference.

Comprehending the impacts of digital transformation on cultural identities is a substantial challenge and opportunity for political decision-makers. This article seeks to enhance comprehension of cultural identities and politics on online platforms within political and social contexts.

FINDINGS AND METHOD

Results

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Digital transformation refers to the process in which significant advancements in communication technology have a profound impact on societal structures. Castells (1996) argued that the proliferation of the Internet has brought about significant transformations in people's lifestyles and social interactions, as observed through the lens of the "network society" notion. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that digital transformation encompasses more than just technological modifications. Jenkins (2006) and Turkle (2011) contend that digital media exerts substantial influence on cultural and social domains. For instance, digital platforms have the potential to enhance social engagement and reshape interpersonal connections through the promotion of participatory cultures. In addition, economists Hess and Ostrom (2007) highlight the economic aspect of digital transformation, asserting that it presents novel economic prospects and difficulties by altering conventional company structures. Politically, digital change has a significant impact on democratic processes and the involvement of citizens in politics. Chadwick (2013) highlights the profound impact of social media on political communication and campaign methods, stressing the necessity for political actors to effectively utilize digital platforms. Nevertheless, scholars like Tufekci (2017) contend that issues such as the improper use of social media and the dissemination of polluted information can have adverse effects on democratic processes. The media exerts its impact on political processes through multiple means, including the formation of political leaders' and parties' public image, as well as the interpretation and analysis of political events. According to Chavez (2019) and Milton (2020), media can enhance political engagement and promote societal transformation. It is crucial to consider the cultural, economic, and political aspects of digital revolution in this situation. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of the intricacy of relationships in these domains may enhance our ability to accurately forecast forthcoming social transformations. Hence, it is imperative for future studies to thoroughly investigate the impacts of digital revolution on social and political domains.

Method

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This investigation was undertaken by thoroughly examining the current literature. Through the utilization of the qualitative research methodology, an analysis was conducted to investigate the political and social ramifications of digital transformation. The primary objective was to ascertain the key discoveries derived from these investigations. This approach is well-suited for offering a comprehensive comprehension of the development of cultural identities on digital platforms and the consequential political and social effects of these identities.

Digital Transformation and Network Society

Digital transformation refers to a profound alteration in the way people live, conduct business, and interact with each other, brought about by the rapid advancement and widespread adoption of information and communication technology. This phenomenon has gained momentum as the internet has become an indispensable aspect of everyday existence, with the technical progress ushered in by the post-modern era. The term "network society" refers to the impact of the digital transformation on social structures. The term "digital society" describes a social framework where individuals engage with one another primarily through digital networks, and where access to information and services is facilitated by digital platforms. Manuel Castells popularized the concept of the network society, which is regarded as one of the most unique forms of social organization in the digital age (Castells, 2010). A prominent characteristic of the network society is that individuals structure their everyday routines using digital platforms. The advent of the Internet, social media, e-commerce platforms, and other digital tools has brought about a profound transformation in the way individuals get information, interact, engage in shopping activities, and socialize (Van Dijk, 2020). This modification allows individuals to engage with each other independent of temporal and spatial constraints. Thanks to social media platforms, individuals may maintain constant communication and effortlessly engage with others who share similar interests, regardless of geographical distance. The influence of digital revolution on social relations is likewise remarkably significant.

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Conventional methods of in-person communication have been substituted by digital communication. Email, instant messaging programs, and video conferencing technologies are utilized extensively in several domains, including both professional and personal spheres (Baym, 2015). This enables the rapid and extensive establishment and maintenance of social bonds. Nevertheless, it has also introduced new obstacles, such as the decline in in-person encounters and the experience of social isolation inside digital settings. The process of developing one's identity in the network society has been altered due to the impact of digital transformation. Online platforms offer abundant opportunity for individuals to articulate themselves and cultivate unique identities. Individuals can construct their digital identities via social media profiles, blogs, and other digital content creation tools. These digital identities can vary from individuals' offline identities and can undergo frequent changes. Digital identities possess a flexible framework that enables individuals to manifest their personalities in diverse manners within different social and cultural environments (Turkle, 1995).

The advent of digital transformation has highlighted disparities in the availability of information and technology. The term "digital divide" refers to the constraints that some individuals and communities have when it comes to using digital technologies (Van Dijk, 2005). This inequality can stem from variables such as educational attainment, socioeconomic status, and geographical placement, and can exert significant impacts on social frameworks. The digital divide exacerbates preexisting social and economic disparities, hence detrimentally impacting social engagement and equal access to opportunities. The ongoing digital change will continue to impact social and political frameworks. The relentless and ongoing progression of technology advancements will consistently transform the qualities and workings of the network society. The ethical utilization of digital technology, the promotion of digital equality, and the enhancement of individuals' digital competencies will be prioritized in this process. To fully capitalize on the beneficial impacts of digital transformation and mitigate its negative consequences, policymakers and all sectors of society must adjust to this process of change.

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Communication Technologies and Social Structure

Digital transformation is the term used to describe the significant impact that rapid advancements in communication technology have on the social structures of societies. This transition arose because of the advancements brought about by the post-modern era and was further expedited by the widespread adoption of the internet. The advancement of communication technologies has facilitated the integration of all aspects of daily life into digital platforms and emphasized the notion of a "network society" (Castells, 2010). The concept of network society refers to a framework in which people engage with one another through digital networks and obtain information and services via digital platforms.

The influence of digital communication on social connections is significant and extensive. Conventional methods of in-person communication have been substituted by digital communication. Email, instant messaging programs, and video conferencing technologies are extensively utilized in both professional and personal contexts. This facilitates the rapid and extensive establishment and maintenance of social relationships. Social media platforms facilitate continuous communication and seamless interaction among individuals who share similar interests, regardless of their physical locations. Nevertheless, the advent of digital communication has also presented novel obstacles, including reduced opportunities for in-person contacts and the potential for social isolation within digital realms. Engaging in relationships through digital platforms might result in the deterioration of conventional social connections and amplify individuals' sense of isolation (Turkle, 2011).

The process of developing one's identity in the network society has been altered due to the impact of digital transformation. Online platforms offer abundant opportunity for individuals to articulate themselves and cultivate unique identities. Individuals can construct their digital identities via social media profiles, blogs, and other digital content creation tools. These digital identities can vary from individuals' offline identities and can frequently fluctuate. Digital identities possess a flexible framework that enables individuals to represent themselves in diverse manners within different social and cultural settings.

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Social media significantly influences the formation of social norms. These platforms enable individuals to promptly respond to social events and issues and connect with wide-ranging audiences. Social media enables rapid coordination and dissemination of social movements and protests (Tufekci, 2017). The media exerts influence on the overall perspectives and political awareness of society, as well as playing a crucial role in shaping social norms (Entman, 2012). The dissemination of trends and components of popular culture through social media platforms can have an impact on individuals' conduct and social engagements. Social media can have a profound impact on social norms, causing them to change quickly and giving rise to the development of new standards. Nevertheless, social media also poses the peril of swift dissemination of false information and deception.

Digital transformation has wide-ranging implications that extend beyond communication and identity creation. It encompasses domains such as social norms, political engagement, and cultural change. The advent of digitalization in societies has brought about a transformation in political involvement and social mobility, giving them a new dimension. Social media platforms have a significant impact on the organization and spread of demands for social change.

Nevertheless, there are apprehensions regarding the societal ramifications of digital revolution. Specifically, the challenges posed by the influence of social media on democratic processes and the spread of misinformation are matters that require sincere attention. The strategic exploitation of social media can exert influence over political decision-making processes and exacerbate social polarization. Within this framework, the societal consequences of digital transformation are intricate and diverse. Although this process brings about revolutionary transformations in communication, it also has a major impact on social norms, political engagement, and cultural frameworks. Hence, comprehending and addressing the societal consequences of digital change necessitates the adoption of a multidisciplinary strategy. By adopting this approach, we may maintain the favorable parts of digitalization while reducing its adverse consequences.

Political Communication and Digital Transformation

Political communication is the transmission of information among political actors, the media, and the public. This process serves crucial roles, such as conveying political messages, shaping public opinion, and spreading political ideas. Political communication is essential for the proper functioning of democracy. It serves crucial purposes such as promoting political engagement, providing information to the public, and assuring political responsibility. Conventional political communication was conducted via media platforms such as newspapers, radio, and television. Nevertheless, the advent of digital transformation has brought about a profound shift in this procedure. The internet's widespread use and the emergence of social media platforms have facilitated more accessible, expedited, and interactive political communication.

Digital platforms provide robust tools for the creation and distribution of political content. Digital platforms such as social media, blogs, video sharing sites, and podcasts empower individuals and political entities to generate and disseminate their own political communications. These platforms facilitate individuals' ability to access and engage with extensive audiences.

Digital platforms provide a direct means for political parties, candidates, and activist groups to engage with voters and supporters. Particularly during election periods, internet platform marketing can be more efficacious than traditional media. The influence of digital communication on changing individuals' political beliefs and attitudes is substantial. Social media enables users to quickly obtain political news and information and speeds up the spread of this information to big groups of people. In addition, digital platforms offer users a venue to articulate their viewpoints and engage in public discourse. However, digital communication also has a drawback: it contributes to political polarization and the creation of "echo chambers". Users frequently engage with individuals who hold similar perspectives, which can result in their developing a propensity to dismiss alternative viewpoints. This has the potential to exacerbate the radicalization of political ideologies and deepen societal divisions.

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Conversely, digital platforms enable marginalized groups and individuals to amplify their views and engage in political processes. This can facilitate the expansion of political involvement and enhance the inclusivity of democratic processes. The reciprocal influence of digital communication has a significant role in contemporary democracies. Political communication has experienced a profound shift in recent times due to the process of digital transformation (Chadwick, 2013). Specifically, the emergence of social media platforms has revolutionized the way political figures and individuals engage in communication and interact with one another. These platforms have a significant impact on enhancing political engagement and spreading political communications. The influence of digital communication on political processes is growing and fundamentally altering the nature of political engagement (Vaccari & Valeriani, 2016). Although social media platforms provide users with easy access to political content, they also promote the expression of political opinions and engagement in social discourse. Within this framework, digital communication is regarded as a crucial instrument in facilitating the democratization of political processes.

THE ROLE OF THE MEDIA AND ITS POLITICAL EFFECTS

The influence of media in shaping social and political norms is undergoing a substantial shift and evolution from traditional to digital platforms. Traditional media, such as television, radio, and newspapers, establish societal norms that influence accepted beliefs and behaviors. However, digital media has significantly transformed this process. Specifically, the creation and distribution of political content by individuals and groups via social media platforms has increased the democratic accessibility of information and diminished the dominance of traditional media monopolies (Castells, 2008). The proliferation of digital media has facilitated the rapid and extensive dissemination of information, hence influencing public opinion. Although social media platforms offer the freedom for users to select their preferred news sources and receive tailored material, this can also result in the creation of "echo chambers" and "filter bubbles". These effects may result in

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individuals being more susceptible to information that aligns with their beliefs and less exposed to contradictory perspectives (Pariser, 2011). Nevertheless, digital media also enables marginalized groups to amplify their voices and facilitates the dissemination of alternate perspectives. This trait allows digital media to have a considerable influence on public opinion, resulting in increased diversity and pluralism (Benkler, 2006). The media's ability to promote engagement in political processes is crucial in democratic societies. Both traditional and digital media play a crucial role in enhancing democratic processes by providing citizens with information, increasing their political consciousness, and promoting active engagement. Specifically, digital media provide a readily available venue for young individuals and marginalized groups that typically do not engage in conventional political activities. According to Loader and Mercea (2011), the involvement of these groups in political processes can be enhanced through social media campaigns, online discussions, and digital activism. The media's role in shaping social and political standards has transformed alongside its evolution. Traditional media often exhibited a biased perspective, which influenced the establishment of societal standards and political ideologies to some degree. Nevertheless, the advent of digital media and social media platforms has expanded individuals' access to a broader spectrum of information and facilitated the expression of their own viewpoints. While this process grants equal access to the media's authority in decision-making, it also empowers individuals to establish their own networks for exchanging information and select content that aligns with their personal perspectives. Nevertheless, this entails some challenges. Social media platforms frequently present users with content that reinforces their existing beliefs, causing them to become resistant to alternative perspectives. Hence, the media's social and political impact encompasses favorable elements like fostering democratic engagement and guaranteeing inclusivity, alongside adverse outcomes such as polarization and restricted dissemination of information.

Digital Identities and Cultural Diversity

Online platforms facilitate the convergence of digital identities and cultural diversity, and significantly contribute to the expression and formation of individual and collective identities. Users can express their cultural identities through numerous means on digital platforms, such as social media, blogs, and forums. These platforms enhance the interactivity and dynamism of identity formation processes by allowing users to engage with various cultural expressions and reinterpret their own identities within this framework. Users can engage with both global and local cultures in digital contexts. This implies that identities are not confined to regional or national frameworks, but rather undergo transformation within a global outlook. The act of expressing and exchanging cultural identities using digital media has become prevalent, particularly among the younger generation. Nevertheless, digital revolution can have both advantageous and detrimental effects on cultural diversity. Digital platforms facilitate the amplification of minority cultures and marginalized groups, enabling them to express their perspectives and advocate for cultural diversity. Nevertheless, the dominance of influential cultural forces over these platforms sometimes results in cultural uniformity and the marginalization of certain cultural expressions. Online identity politics influences the political and social dynamics of identities formed and exchanged on digital platforms. These regulations address the process of individuals establishing their online personas, how they are viewed by others, and the significance of these personas in social interactions. Digital platforms are crucial in the realm of political activism and social movements. These platforms offer essential resources for individuals and collectives to articulate their political opinions and coordinate. Nevertheless, online identity politics can exacerbate social polarization and give rise to issues such as the dissemination of misinformation and the proliferation of hate speech in the digital realm.

Political and Social Consequences of Digital Transformation

The process of digital transformation has a major impact on the way individuals engage in political and social activities. Online identities provide individuals with novel chances to articulate their political opinions, engage in political discourse, and endorse social movements (Bennett & Segerberg, 2012). Young people heavily utilize online forums for political engagement. Nevertheless, certain individuals are hindered from engaging equally in political processes due to constraints such as limited internet access and lack of digital literacy (Norris, 2001).

Digital platforms possess the capacity to either safeguard or stifle cultural and political diversity. These venues have the capacity to promote social and political diversity by facilitating the expression of views from minority groups and marginalized populations (Castells, 2009). It is important to be cautious about the potential influence of commercial and political factors on content moderation rules and algorithms, as this could result in the marginalization of certain perspectives and cultural expressions (Gillespie, 2018). Social media networks provide customized content by monitoring and analyzing users' interactions. This may result in individuals being exposed exclusively to content that reinforces their existing beliefs and hence remaining within echo chambers. Consequently, there is a possibility that social polarization will intensify, making it challenging to engage in meaningful conversations between individuals with differing perspectives (Sunstein, 2001). The future impact of digital transformation on political and social systems will be determined by the pace and trajectory of technical advancements. Technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, and blockchain have the potential to fundamentally transform political processes and societal dynamics. Nevertheless, there is a potential for exacerbating socioeconomic disparities during this course of action. Disparities in the availability of technical advancements can result in an expansion of the digital gap among different social strata (Van Dijk, 2020). When formulating future policy, it is crucial to consider the reciprocal impacts of digital revolution. Furthermore, it is imperative to tackle concerns such as digital disparities and

polarization, while simultaneously promoting democratic engagement and fostering social inclusivity.

Conclusion

Past study in the literature has extensively analyzed the social and political ramifications of digital revolution. The discussion mostly focuses on the impact of online identities on political involvement. Online platforms serve as a crucial medium for individuals to articulate their political opinions and engage in political activities. Nevertheless, the absence of internet connectivity and limited knowledge of digital technologies may hinder the fair and equal engagement in political activities. Hence, it is imperative to implement policy measures that foster digital inclusivity and mitigate digital disparities. Furthermore, the discourse revolves around safeguarding or repressing diversity on digital platforms. Digital platforms have the potential to significantly contribute to the promotion and preservation of cultural and political diversity. Nevertheless, due to the impact of content filtering policies and algorithms, there is a potential for some perspectives and cultural forms of expression to be neglected. Hence, it is imperative to create policies that provide transparency and accountability in relation to content moderation and algorithm design. The potential societal and political impacts of digital revolution were analyzed. The speed and direction of technical innovations can have a considerable impact on political processes and social dynamics. Nevertheless, there is a potential for exacerbating social disparities in this undertaking. Hence, it is imperative to implement legislative measures aimed at mitigating disparities in technology access and bolstering digital democracy. An in-depth analysis is required to fully understand the intricate social and political ramifications of digital revolution. To establish a fair and all-encompassing digital landscape, it is imperative for policymakers and civil society to collaborate harmoniously. It is crucial to implement rules that promote collaboration among technological corporations, academia, governments, and non-governmental organizations in this situation. By implementing digital transformation, the beneficial impacts on social and political domains can be enhanced while

minimizing the detrimental repercussions.

However, it is crucial for future studies to concentrate on domains to gain a more profound understanding of the social and political consequences of digital revolution. Within this framework, the subsequent suggestions can be considered:

-Assessment of Digital Participation: In order to gain a deeper comprehension of the impact of digital transformation on political involvement, it is necessary to conduct research that assess the level of digital participation across different demographic categories.

-Analyzing Digital Polarization: Further investigation is necessary to comprehend the impact of digital revolution on social polarization. Topics covered may encompass algorithmic categorization, filter bubbles, and information echo chambers.

-Examining Digital Disparities: Further investigation is necessary to gain a deeper comprehension of the impact of digital transformation on social disparities. An in-depth analysis of disparities in digital literacy, internet connectivity, and technological accessibility is of utmost significance.

Considering the societal and political ramifications of digital change, it is crucial for policymakers and social administrators to heed the subsequent suggestions:

-Digital Literacy Training: Efforts should be made to develop education and awareness programs aimed at enhancing the digital literacy level of society. This can facilitate individuals

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in being more cognizant and discerning about digital settings.

- The development of internet access and technology infrastructure is necessary to mitigate disparities in digital access. Ensuring digital connectivity is particularly crucial in remote regions and economically disadvantaged groups.

-Enhancing Data Privacy and Security Policies: It is imperative to develop more robust policies and regulations to safeguard data privacy and security in digital settings. By implementing this measure, the security and privacy of individuals' personal data may be guaranteed, thereby ensuring a secure and risk-free experience in digital settings.

RESTRICTION

The research is limited to scientific research that has been previously conducted and published in the literature.

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